

Microgeometrical Effects on the Elastoplastic Behavior of Particle Reinforced MMCs

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ABSTRACT

A unit cell approach is used to investigate the influence of inclusion arrangements and shapes on the mechanical and thermo-mechanical behavior of particle reinforced MMCs. Two approaches are compared, 2/D-axisymmetric and 3/D modelling. All cubic arrangements, simple cubic as well as face and body centered cubic, give an anisotropic response. Whereas the investigated tensile loading directions do not strongly influence the response of fcc and bcc configurations, simple cubic arrangements show a marked anisotropy. The thermal expansion behavior in the considered configurations is very similar when cubic or spherical inclusions are used with the 3/D models. However, 2/D-axisymmetric models as well as cylindrical inclusions in 3/D-model introduce noticeable changes in the predicted overall response.

Keywords: MMC, Unit Cells, Particle Reinforcements, Particle Arrangements

1. INTRODUCTION

Particle reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC) are of high technical and economic interest, because they combine improved stiffness to weight ratio, decreased thermal expansion, and high wear resistance compared to the unreinforced material with attractive production costs. On the one hand, much theoretical work on this class of composites has been based on mean field approaches (the Mori-Tanaka type expressions of Wakashima [1] used for reference in the present work belong to this group), and, on the other hand, periodic arrangements of particles have been investigated by analytical (e.g. [2]) and numerical methods. The latter typically take the form of unit cell based homogenization approaches using the Finite Element Method for computing the microscale stress and strain distributions in an appropriate reference volume. Plane 2/D [3], axisymmetric 2/D [4,5] and 3/D models [6] have been reported in the literature. Because investigations of short fiber [7] and continuously [8] reinforced composites have shown a marked dependence of both microscopic and macroscopic responses to the inclusion arrangements, similar effects can be expected to play an important role in particle reinforced materials, and the present work is aimed at comparing selected particle arrangements and shapes with respect to their influence on the predicted behavior. Because particle reinforced composites generally show an isotropic overall response [9], special emphasis is put on the discussion of the overall symmetry of the investigated models.

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1 3/D Modelling

Different spatial arrangements of various inclusions in MMCs are investigated by the Finite Element Method [10] using a unit cell approach. As typical inclusions, spherical, cylindrical, and cubic particles are considered in simple cubic (sc), face centered cubic (fcc) and body centered cubic (bcc) arrangements. Two different types of 3/D unit cells are used for the computations. The first kind contains parts of two inclusions and can represent the response in two different sets of directions, parallel to a side of the cube (0°) and in the direction of a face diagonal (45°), respectively. The second unit cell, which contains only one inclusion, is smaller and more efficient for computations, but the load directions are limited to the 0° -case and hydrostatic loading. As an example, unit cells for an fcc arrangement of spherical inclusions are shown in fig.1.

The boundary conditions (B.C.) for the two-particle unit cell must be prescribed in such a way that under the loads considered here the surfaces are always parallel or at right angles to each other, i.e. the deformed structure must remain a parallelepiped. The same set of B.C. is used for the one-particle unit cell in the simple cubic arrangement.

FIG.1: a) fcc arrangement of spherical inclusions with two different unit cells and b) deformed structure of the one-particle fcc unit cell

FIG.2: Two-particle unit cells for a) sc-arrangement/cubic inclusions, b) fcc-arrangement/cylindrical inclusions, c) bcc-arrangement/spherical inclusions

The B.C. for the one-inclusion unit cell representing bcc and fcc arrangements may be considered as a 3/D development of the point symmetry conditions developed by Tvergaard [5] for axisymmetric models. The reference volume consists of four unit cells, each containing one particle. Whereas the B.C. for the reference volume as a whole correspond to those for the two-particle unit cell described above, line symmetry conditions must be enforced on the interior faces of each subcell to satisfy symmetry requirements. For the configuration shown in fig.1b this corresponds to the following conditions:

$$u_z(B, y, z) = -u_z(B, y, L - z) \quad (1)$$

$$u_z(x, B, z) = -u_z(x, B, L - z) \quad (2)$$

$$u_z(x, y, L) = -u_z(x, y, 0) = U_z \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, compatibility within the reference volume requires that the total cross-sectional area of four neighboring subcells is independent of the “axial” (i.e. the z -) coordinate, which leads to additional conditions:

$$u_x(B, y, z) + u_x(B, y, L - z) = 2u_x(B, y, L/2) = 2U_x \quad (4)$$

$$u_y(x, B, z) + u_y(x, B, L - z) = 2u_y(x, B, L/2) = 2U_y \quad (5)$$

The symmetry lines at $z=L/2$ and at $x=y=b$ have to remain straight in all deformed states:

$$u_x(B, y, L/2) = u_x(B, B, z) = U_x \quad (6)$$

$$u_y(x, B, L/2) = u_y(B, B, z) = U_y \quad (7)$$

$$u_z(B, y, L/2) = u_z(x, B, L/2) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Here U_x, U_y, U_z are master deformations in the $x-, y-, z$ -directions, and L and B are the height and side length, respectively, of each unit cell. The types of inclusion selected for investigation are spheres with a diameter $d=5\mu\text{m}$, cubes with a side length $d=5\mu\text{m}$ and cylinders with diameter and length $d=l=5\mu\text{m}$. The inclusion volume fraction of the MMCs is kept constant at 20% by selecting appropriate dimensions of the unit cells.

2.2 2/D Modelling

As a less costly alternative to the 3/D cubic models, periodic arrays of particles in a matrix can be approximated by arrangements of cylindrical unit cells, which correspond to staggered or unstaggered square arrangements of inclusions [5,7]. The lengths L of such axisymmetric unit cells are selected to correspond to specific cubic arrangements and the radii R are chosen to give the appropriate cross sectional area. In this sense the unstaggered (un) configuration is equivalent to an sc arrangement, and the two staggered geometries (stf and stb) considered here correspond to fcc and bcc, respectively.

The staggered and unstaggered arrangements use similar meshes but different B.C. The deformed shape of an unstaggered unit cell has to be a circular cylinder, i.e. the “outside” deformations $u_r(R, z) = U_r$ and $u_z(r, L) = U_z$ have to be constant over z and r , respectively (see fig.3). Here U_r and U_z are master deformations of the unit cell. The model for the staggered unit cell configurations uses point symmetry axial B.C. on the outside with respect to a pivot point C ($R, L/2$) as proposed by Tvergaard [5]:

$$u_z(R, z) = -u_z(R, L - z) \quad (9)$$

$$u_z(r, L) = -u_z(r, 0) = U_z \quad (10)$$

The radial compatibility condition, which requires that the total cross-sectional area of two neighboring cells is independent of the axial coordinate [5] can be linearized to give [7]:

$$u_r(R, z) + u_r(R, L - z) = 2u_r(R, L/2) = 2U_r \quad (11)$$

It should be pointed out that this approach can be extended to cover regular patterns of two or more different inclusions similar to models proposed for short fiber reinforcements [7].

FIG.3: 2/D unit cell arrangement

The material data correspond to SiC particles embedded in commercially pure Al with a perfect interface. The particles are assumed to behave thermo-elastically and a thermo-elastic-plastic material law with isotropic hardening is used for the matrix. Both components are assumed to be isotropic. The following input data are used for both components: Young's modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν , and the total coefficient of thermal expansion α_t . The yield stress σ_Y and the hardening modulus E_t are needed for the matrix only. No relaxation or creep effects are included. The material data used are shown in tab.1, where (p) denotes the particles and (m) the matrix.

T [°C]	$E^{(p)}$ [MPa]	$\nu^{(p)}$ []	$\alpha_t^{(p)}$ [K ⁻¹]
20	4.290×10^5	0.170	4.30×10^{-6}
200	4.270×10^5	0.160	4.73×10^{-6}
400	4.230×10^5	0.145	5.21×10^{-6}

T [°C]	$E^{(m)}$ [MPa]	$\nu^{(m)}$ []	$\sigma_Y^{(m)}$ [MPa]	$E_t^{(m)}$ [MPa]	$\alpha_t^{(m)}$ [K ⁻¹]
0	6.750×10^4	0.35	28.6	720	2.2750×10^{-5}
20	6.720×10^4	0.35	28.2	638	2.3000×10^{-5}
50	6.650×10^4	0.35	27.4	525	2.3300×10^{-5}
100	6.525×10^4	0.35	25.9	367	2.3769×10^{-5}
150	6.325×10^4	0.35	23.8	264	2.4223×10^{-5}
200	6.000×10^4	0.35	21.1	199	2.4675×10^{-5}
250	5.438×10^4	0.35	17.4	158	2.5126×10^{-5}
300	4.675×10^4	0.35	13.5	125	2.5577×10^{-5}
350	3.900×10^4	0.35	10.1	100	2.6027×10^{-5}
400	3.138×10^4	0.35	7.3	78	2.6484×10^{-5}

TAB.1: Material data of SiC-particles and Al99.9-matrix.

3. TENSILE LOADING

For the evaluation of the isothermal mechanical behavior axial tensile loading up to 50MPa nominal tensile stress is simulated. The global mechanical behavior of the composite is characterized by the stress-strain curve.

3.1 Different Arrangements of Spherical Inclusions

The differences between the overall stress-strain curves of the investigated configurations (with spherical inclusions) are noticeable, even in the elastic range (fig.4, tab.2). The stiffest response is found for the 0°-direction (parallel to the cube axes) of the sc configuration. The 0°-Young's modulus is about 10% higher than the 45°-value (loading in the direction of an sc face diagonal), which is due to the marked anisotropy of this arrangement [11]. It is worth noting that the 45°-response is close to the mean field predictions obtained from Wakashima's approach [1]. The higher stiffness gives rise to lower plastic deformations at the maximum load of 50MPa. On the microscale, higher constraint effects in the region between the two inclusions cause very high hydrostatic stress states for the loading in the 0°-direction, which stiffen the hardening response to an external load. The predictions for the fcc and bcc arrangements (which are similar to each other) display less pronounced anisotropy effects.

FIG.4: Stress-strain relationships for spherical inclusions in sc, fcc, and bcc arrangements (tensile loading up to 50MPa)

A comparison with the analytical computations shows that the mean field phase stresses cannot capture the maxima and minima of the microstress state. Consequently, the periodic microfield approximations predict the onset of yielding well before overall yielding is found by the mean field theory. The differences between these two types of prediction for the yield limit are more pronounced than in long fiber [12] and short fiber [7] reinforced MMCs.

After comparison of the different unit cells it can be concluded that the anisotropy effects, which are present in all cubic configurations, are most pronounced for the sc arrangement. Specifically, models combining sc symmetry with loading in the 0°-direction should not be used for modelling particle reinforced composites, because they will overpredict the overall stiffness of the material. The other configurations represent the behavior of particle reinforced MMCs more satisfactorily.

FIG.5: Stress-strain relationships for spherical and cubic inclusions in sc, fcc, and bcc arrangements (tensile loading in 0° -direction up to 50MPa)

3.2 Different Inclusion Geometries

The shape of the reinforcement is not well defined in real particle reinforced MMCs. However, the global and microscale responses of the composite are affected by this parameter. Among the three particle shapes considered in this paper, the spherical inclusions, which typically form the basis of analytical approaches, have the highest degree of symmetry. The cubic particles are an extreme case for inclusions with sharp corners. In the models used here, both cubic and cylindrical inclusions are aligned with the faces of the reference volume.

The stress-strain relations obtained for spherical, cylindrical, and cubic inclusions in fcc and sc arrangements are plotted in fig.5. The differences between the inclusion types can be observed in both the elastic and the plastic regime. The spherical inclusions give rise to a softer response whereas cylindrical and cubic inclusions produce a stiffer overall behavior.

3.3 2/D Modelling

The axisymmetric models can only be used with spherical and cylindrical inclusions. In contrast to the cubic arrangements, they display a transversely isotropic symmetry. The overall stress-strain curves predicted for loading parallel to the axis of symmetry are shown in fig.6.

FIG.6: Stress-strain relationships for spherical inclusions in sc, fcc, and bcc arrangements as well as staggered and unstaggered axisymmetric models (tensile loading up to 50MPa, 0°)

The response of the unstaggered axisymmetric model can be seen to be similar to that of the sc arrangement loaded in the 0° -direction and consequently it is also too stiff. From the staggered models (with particle distances corresponding to fcc and bcc, respectively) much softer responses are obtained, with the Young's moduli being slightly lower than those of the corresponding 3/D models, and yielding takes place at lower loads.

	3/D- 0°	3/D- 45°	axisym.
spherical inclusions/sc-arrangement	96.40	90.29	96.44
spherical inclusions/fcc-arrangement	90.56	91.58	88.62
spherical inclusions/bcc-arrangement	90.04	–	88.23
cylindrical inclusions/sc-arrangement	102.57	91.74	102.33
cylindrical inclusions/fcc-arrangement	94.54	91.38	92.02
cubic inclusions/sc-arrangement	101.00	92.14	–
cubic inclusions/fcc-arrangement	94.39	93.83	–
mean field solution [1]	91.20	91.20	–

TAB.2: Young's moduli [GPa] predicted for different particle arrangements

4. THERMAL LOADING

MMCs are often used in environments subject to cyclic temperature changes. Hence, an understanding of their behavior under thermal loading is essential. For the evaluation of the overall thermo-mechanical behavior the response to a temperature loading cycle ($20^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow 400^\circ\text{C} \rightarrow 20^\circ\text{C}$) is studied. The results are given in the form of strain-temperature relationships.

In contrast to the mechanical response, the overall thermal expansion behavior of the three cubic configurations shows neither a significant dependence on the particle arrangements nor noticeable anisotropy effects for spherical and cubic inclusions. The thermal expansion response of the axisymmetrical arrangements is transversely isotropic, with the axial and transverse predictions bracketing the 3/D results, see fig.7a. Aligned cylindrical inclusions are computed to cause a noticeable deviation from the isotropic behavior in both the 2/D axisymmetric and the 3/D models, compare fig.7b.

FIG.7: Strain-temperature relationships for a) spherical/sc and unstaggered arrangement, b) cylindrical/bcc and bcc-like staggered arrangement

5. CONCLUSIONS

Among the configurations considered here, the best descriptions for the overall response of particle reinforced MMCs were obtained from fcc and bcc arrangements, with staggered axisymmetric models also giving quite satisfactory results. These approaches are also in good agreement with mean field predictions. Due to their marked anisotropy, 3/D models based on simple cubic particle arrangements as well as unstaggered axisymmetric approaches, however, predict overly stiff responses in both elastic and inelastic regimes.

Under thermal loading, cubic arrangements do not display anisotropy in the elastic range with cubic or spherical inclusions. Due to their transversely isotropic symmetry, the 2/D axisymmetrical models do not adequately represent the behavior of particle reinforced MMC. The same can be observed for cylindrical inclusions.

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